

LIBRARY AND BOOK TRADE ALMANAC

AUTHORITY

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- Sub. Title : Facts, Figures, & report
- Editor: Rebecca L.Thomas, Bear, Catherin
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INTRODUCTION

The American library and book trade annual, later renamed the Bowker Annual: Library book trade almanac is a resource for librarians, publisher, and booksellers that provide reviews of key trend , events, and developments in the industry , statistics on book prices, number of books

published, library expenditures, and average salaries, explanations of new library legislation and changes in funding programs and other information.

Library and Book Trade Almanac includes federal reports, such as the national centre for education statistics , library statistic program, library legislation, accredited master' s programs scholarships, library and library book trade research and statics, distinguish books and other media, and a directory of organisation.

SCOPE

1. Aim a compilation of informed analysis and practical information of interest to the library, information and book trade communities.
2. It also includes reviews of the year ' s news and trends in public libraries, school libraries and publishing and reports on the activities of federal agencies, and national and international library and publishing organisation.
3. Library and Book Trade Almanac is comprised of information for library and information science professionals.

TREATMENT

1. A full calendar events, key organization, names and number of individuals including e- mails addresses fax number and much more.
2. It including placement sources, sources, and scholarship resources for library and information science professionals
3. It includes library legislation activities of grant – making agencies and funding programs that support libraries.

4. Provides help to research and statistics on libraries and the book trade, including library expenditure and state ranking , book sales statistics.
5. Reference information : lists of bestsellers, recommended books and other media major literary prize winners of the past year and information on obtaining an ISBN, ISSN and SAN.
6. Directory of library and publishing organisation at the state , national and international levels, plus calendar of major upcoming events.

ARRANGEMENT

1. Book is not arranged in alphabetical order
2. Chronological arrangement with latest updates
3. Books are divided into different parts.

FORMAT

1. It is available in print format.
2. It is available in hard binding.
3. Single volume.

DRAWBACKS

1. Books are not available in online.
2. Books are not available in CD room.

CONCLUSION

In last , library and book trade almanac is a fully updated reference tool make it easy to stay on the top of the development that affect libraries, bookseller and publisher alike and find answer to the countless on the job question.It remain preminent for librarians and booksellers.

REFERENCE

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2. <http://books.google.co.in>
3. <http://www.archive.org.in>
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